

Machine Learning–Powered Model for Detection of Early Knee Osteoarthritis on Anteroposterior Radiographs Using a Smart Mask Technique

Background:

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) represents a substantial global healthcare burden, particularly in moderate to severe stages that often necessitate surgical intervention. This study aims to evaluate the preliminary performance of a machine learning (ML) model utilizing a novel smart mask technique for detecting early-stage knee OA changes on anteroposterior radiographs.

Methods:

A total of 208 anteroposterior knee radiographs were collected and allocated into training, validation, and testing datasets at proportions of 80%, 10%, and 10%, respectively, using Roboflow 3.0 (Fast), compatible with YOLOv8 architecture. Image annotation was performed using a smart mask labeling technique, categorizing each image into two classes based on the Kellgren–Lawrence (KL) grading system: KL 0–2 (early stage: no significant change to mild OA) and KL 3–4 (moderate to severe OA). Model performance was primarily evaluated using mean average precision (mAP).

Results:

The model demonstrated a mean average precision (mAP) of 78% overall, with class-specific performance of 96% for KL 0–2 and 60% for KL 3–4.

Conclusion:

The ML-powered model employing a smart mask technique shows excellent performance in detecting early-stage knee OA (KL 0–2). Further development should focus on improving detection performance for more advanced stages (KL 3–4).

Figure 1. The annotation is shown with a smart mask technique.

Figure 2. External validation shows KL0-2 detection on an anteroposterior radiograph of the left knee.